

THE SPECIAL FEATURES OF THE SOUND STRUCTURE IN THE GERMAN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The word is one of the basic building blocks of language. Man speaks and writes in words. When someone makes a verbal utterance, they string together forms of words. He links them to form larger units. In written language these are sentences and texts, in spoken language these are functional units, contributions to conversations and conversations.

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Words play a special role not only for speaking and writing, but also for dealing with language and for imparting knowledge. When someone translates something from one language into another, they need to know which words correspond to each other. If someone wants to find out more about something, they look it up in a dictionary or encyclopedia. No linguistic unit is as well known to the speakers of a language as the word. The word is regarded as a linguistic unit par excellence.

Every word has a form side and a content (meaning) side. The form side can be seen as a series of sounds in speech. In written languages, it consists of a sequence of letters in alphabetized languages. The task of grammar is to describe the form and meaning of words. The grammar explains which regularities are followed by the construction of forms and the construction of meanings and how form and meaning are related to each other. Only when you know the regularities does it become understandable that the speakers effortlessly master the many thousands of words in their vocabulary.

German changes, but the regularities that determine the structure of the words also change. This is the case with all languages. In addition, German is in contact with many other languages by which it has been influenced and which it has influenced itself. The simplest form of influencing is the borrowing of words or parts of words. German borrowed, and still borrows, mainly from Greek, Latin, French and English.

Many words are known to be borrowed and where they are borrowed from. Words like commitment or necklace obviously come from French, such as jazz and playback from English.

They have properties that "typical German" words do not have, for example the nasalized vowels in engagement or the initial sound combination [dz] in jazz. Other words are also noticeable, but few speakers know which languages their parts come from. Rhythm is orthographically out of the ordinary, elative (the highest, absolute degree of adjective, also a case of languages such as Finnish) has a little-known meaning, and Pteranodon also has a difficult-to-pronounce sound sequence, which in German is at the beginning of a syllable does not occur.

A speaker of German can therefore recognize words as foreign even if they do not know where they come from. He recognizes such words by certain features of their form or side of meaning by comparing them with the properties of German words. However, it is not the case that all borrowed words have such abnormalities. If you don't have special knowledge, you will hardly guess that window comes from Latin, start from English and furniture from French. These words are integrated into the German vocabulary with all their properties. They do not require special attention.

On the other hand, the words mentioned above are not fully integrated. They have characteristics that identify them as foreign. In order to understand their construction, one has to look beyond the regularities that apply to the vocabulary in the core area of German. In Duden grammar, such words are meant outside of today's core area when foreign words or non-native words are spoken of.

It is not always easy to decide which words and thus which regularities in a language belong to the native (native) vocabulary. Finally, the core area also includes words that were originally borrowed (window, start, furniture). In terms of their properties, they no longer differ from other words in the native vocabulary. That is why the distinction native/non-native (native/foreign) in this book refers primarily to the contemporary properties of the words and not to their origin.

The phonetic structure as well as the written structure of words can be represented in a simple and plausible way if one distinguishes the basic regularities in the core area from the special regularities in the outer areas (the periphery).

The smallest components of the spoken word are the sounds. Most speakers only realize that its word form can be seen as a series of sounds when they learn to write and read. From the sequence of letters in the written word, they deduce the sequence of sounds in the spoken word, even if an assignment is not always easy.

The description of the sounds themselves is based on how they are articulated. The description must be at least accurate enough to distinguish each sound of the language from each other. Only articulatory differences that can be heard are taken into account, because the ear must be able to distinguish every sound in a language from every other sound in that language. The words rudder and luder differ by exactly one sound. If a speaker cannot articulate the difference between l and r or if a listener cannot hear it, then there are difficulties in understanding.

Like many other languages, German uses the Latin alphabet for its orthography. For example, in order to repeat the pronunciation of German words clearly, sound by sound, the alphabet should have more letters. German has more sounds than letters in the alphabet. So you can clearly hear a difference between the o in oven and that in open, but both correspond to the same letter.

In order to record the sound structure of words, one must therefore reproduce their pronunciation more precisely than is possible with the Latin alphabet. In addition, one wants to represent the pronunciation in such a way that it can be compared with the

pronunciation of words in other languages. This purpose is served by special phonetic scripts (phonetic scripts/phonetic alphabets), which contain many more characters than the alphabet of German orthography. The International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) has found the widest distribution among the phonetics (IPA 1996). The IPA is reproduced in full in the Duden pronunciation dictionary (2000).

The IPA provides a sign for every conceivable speech sound. With this phonetic transcription, all words from all languages can be written regardless of the orthography of the respective language. The o in oven, for example, is written as [o] after the IPA, that in open as [ɔ]. In order to distinguish the characters of the phonetic transcription from the letters of the alphabet, they are placed in square brackets.

As with the determination of the graphemes, one can proceed independently of the sound in the entire word graphematics. It is easily possible to describe the structure of graphematic words as if the phonological words, which are largely built up in parallel, did not exist at all. Such an analysis is of considerable theoretical interest and is a prerequisite for the solution of certain practical problems. For example, you have to carry out such analyzes if you want to know whether certain areas of orthography are regular or not.

For practical purposes in general, it is not so much the structure of what is written that is of interest, but rather the relationship between what is written and what is spoken. In what follows, emphasis will be placed on this point. The key question will be how the structure of the graphematic word relates to that of the phonological word. The direction of gaze is on the written as in writing spoken, and only occasionally on the spoken as in reading of written.

The phonemes can be regularly assigned to segments of what is written, namely graphemes (phonographic principle). The assignment rules are called grapheme-phoneme correspondence rules (GPK rules). A GPK rule determines which segment of writing normally corresponds to a particular phoneme. A GPK rule has the form [x...x]-(y...y). Here x...x are phonemes and y...y are graphemes. A phoneme can

therefore be assigned a simple grapheme or a sequence of graphemes. In German, in most cases, a phoneme is assigned exactly one grapheme. In the following, the GPK rules are formulated separately for vowels and consonants. A use case is given as an example for each rule.

Since the representation of the phoneme system is not based on a distinction between course and long vowels but on that between tense and lax vowels, the GPK rules must also operate with tense and lax instead of long and short vowels. A long vowel results when no tense vowel is stressed.

The beginning of the graphematic word form (cabinet) is now compared with this. Regarding the (r), it forms a minimal pair with, for example, (slender). If you now try to break down the sequence of letters (sch) further, you will not succeed, ie it forms a unit. It occupies a place otherwise occupied by graphemes consisting only of a letter. There are many minimal pairs of the type (closet)-(sick), (grit)-(bread), (blue), (chatter)-(chatter). (sch) turns out to be a grapheme s must be included in the inventory of graphemes without decomposition.

With the help of minimal pair analysis and other methods, the graph inventory of German can be determined as a whole. Without presenting all the analysis steps in detail, the following graph inventory can be used

The graphemes in this table are sufficient to cover by far the largest part of the native vocabulary. If a larger vocabulary is to be recorded, which includes many proper names and foreign words, then additional graphemes are needed, such as the vowel grapheme (y) and the consonant grapheme (c). Numerous multigraphs can also be allowed, such as (th), (ph), (ea), (ui), etc. As in phonology, the scope of the inventory depends on this. Which words should still be considered.

REFERENCES:

1. Зиндер Л. П., Строева Т.В «Современный немецкий язык». Москва, 1957.
2. Щерба Л. В «Опыт общей теории лексикографии». Moscow, 1957.
3. Stepanova MD Sernyseva II «Lexicology of the German language». Moscow.